

Making ontologies in the humanities more visible and accessible using SKOS

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Context

Over the past two decades the importance of Knowledge Organization Systems (KOS) within the humanities has grown, starting with the interoperability promised and enabled by Semantic Web standards in the 2000s and continuing with the emergence of FAIR Data Principles and the prevalence of data-intensive research in the 2010s. At the same time, these advancements have pushed against the limits of the term KOS, both its definition and the objects it covers. In recent years, semantic artefact has emerged as an alternative (Jonquet et al., 2023) offering a more up-to-date definition that expands the types of objects covered and aligns with both private and public sector practices as well as the goals of international research efforts (Corcho et al., 2024; Le Franc et al., 2020).

Regardless of how we label them, these products of research hold a special importance in that they are both key to achieving FAIR-ness in the data being produced by research and are themselves research objects that should be FAIR (Cox et al., 2021), yet the latter is often less considered than the former (Poveda-Villalón et al., 2020). This is apparent in the Italian context, which interests us and where semantic artefacts such as ontologies hold a place of importance within humanities, and especially Digital Humanities (DH), research yet can often be difficult to share, find, and (re)use. Existing efforts to make semantic artefacts more visible and reusable have largely focused on the use of organizational systems – from libraries to catalogues and repositories – identified early on as an important component of Semantic Web infrastructure and which have today become all the more essential, if not mandatory, as the amount and usage of semantic artefacts continues to grow in the humanities and other fields (Jonquet et al., 2023).

Purpose

In this paper, we present /DH.arc Vocabularies, a new repository developed to improve the visibility and FAIR-ness of the semantic artefacts produced by the Digital Humanities Advanced Research Centre (/DH.arc) at the University of Bologna, and built using the open-source Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) browser Skosmos. Of particular interest we think is a process for overlaying ontologies written in Web Ontology Language (OWL) with SKOS in order to enable their browsing via the Skosmos interface, which, to our knowledge, offers a novel approach to existing uses of Skosmos in the fields of cultural heritage and DH.

Methods

The original driver for the creation of /DH.arc Vocabularies was the need to make the controlled vocabularies created by the KNOT pilot project available (Fintoni, 2024), thus completing the checklist from Cox et al. to ensure their FAIR-ness. This led us to evaluate various solutions before considering Skosmos as a simple, flexible, and user-friendly solution with existing use cases in the humanities (notably the ACDH-CH's Vocab repository). Following early tests using the KNOT vocabularies, as well as those created for the National Edition of Aldo Moro's Works, we decided to try and widen the usage of Skosmos to include all semantic artefacts created by /DH.arc, including ontologies.

However, Skosmos requires semantic artefacts to be formatted in SKOS (with some support for non-SKOS properties and classes defined using RDF) which led us to look at existing work and examples on the usage of both languages, which was limited. While the majority of existing Skosmos implementations are dedicated to making only controlled vocabularies and similar SKOS-friendly KOS available, *finto.fi* (a service of the National Library of Finland from which the Skosmos application emerged) does make explicit reference to ontologies in its front-end and documentation. We investigated their SKOS representations of ontologies and found them to mainly consist of traditional KOS concepts represented as instances of *owl:Class* that are themselves subclasses of *skos:Concept*, alongside a handful of OWL object and data type properties used to indicate labelling types and deprecated concepts. This approach is well suited to SKOS formatting as none of the concepts in their ontologies require the inclusion of more formal semantics as might be found in an OWL-formatted ontology. However, the ontologies we are interested in making available are OWL-formatted and it is the formal semantics the language makes possible and the ontological commitment in a domain these ontologies express (Bruseker et al., 2017) that should be made evident to the end user for their publication and browsing to be useful (beyond making them FAIR).

To solve this issue, we took inspiration from a 2008 W3C document (related to Jupp et al.) that indicates four patterns for working with SKOS and OWL including going from more (OWL) to less (SKOS) formal by either overlaying the two languages or transforming one into the other.

Findings

We tested both approaches and settled on overlaying, whereby triples are merged, as this allowed us to make our ontologies viewable in the Skosmos browser (which requires SKOS classes and properties in order to display the underlying RDF triples) while ensuring that the formal semantics they offer are still understandable to both humans and machines. This approach implies two key points: the resulting ontologies are necessarily OWL Full and *skos:Concept* and *owl:Class* cannot be disjoint.

We kept our overlaying approach light by only adding the necessary SKOS elements to make use of the Skosmos browser functionalities: each OWL class and property in the original ontologies are given the additional *skos:Concept* class and a *skos:prefLabel* (a duplicate of *rdfs:label*); definitions of OWL specific properties, such as *rdfs:domain* and *rdfs:range*, are added to the file in order for them to also be displayed in the front-end and the same applies to *rdfs:subClassOf* which replaces SKOS semantic relation properties (*skos:broader*, *skos:narrower*) to not confuse any potential subclass structure within the ontology with a more rigid, hierarchical KOS structure; lastly, the ontology is defined as both an *owl:Ontology* and

skos:ConceptScheme while concept scheme-specific properties, such as *skos:hasTopConcept* and *skos:inScheme*, are included at the ontology and class levels to enable proper browsing via the Skosmos interface. We also add some properties from DCAT and FOAF at the ontology/concept scheme level to indicate the projects which developed the ontologies as well as provide links to the original OWL version of the files, so that both are available to users.

Value

The development and release of the /DH.arc Vocabularies semantic artefact repository offers an example of how existing software solutions can be adapted to the needs of smaller DH centers and institutions to enhance the FAIR-ness of their semantic artefacts by using existing infrastructure, staff, and technical skill levels to help make these research products more visible and reusable, a challenge that the humanities must contend with. While the overlaying of OWL and SKOS we have developed for our publishing process works well for simple OWL ontologies, such as the ones currently included in the repository, the approach nonetheless has limits for ontologies with more intricate formal semantics that simply cannot be reproduced in SKOS (such as restrictions). This is something we are working on in the next phase of work (for example by using SKOS notation properties to indicate semantics to an end user), alongside full documentation for how to access the API and the implementation of a documented internal workflow for conversion and publication of future ontologies and other semantic artefacts to ensure their timely addition to the repository.

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